

NOTES

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	R	R ₁	R ₂	Mol. formula	Yield %	M.p. °C	δ (ppm)
2a	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	—	—	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	90	182	3.87 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.5 (2H, s, CH ₂ Cl), 7.0 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 10Hz, C ₂ and C ₆ , Ar-H), 7.8 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 10Hz, C ₃ and C ₅ , Ar-H)
2b	Isonicotinoyl	—	—	C ₈ H ₈ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	95	95	4.8 (2H, s, CH ₂ Cl), 8.4–9.0 (4H, m, protons of pyridine ring)
3a	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	—	—	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	55	92	3.7 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.53 (3H, s, CH ₂ Cl), 6.0 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 9.5Hz, C ₂ and C ₆ , Ar-H), 7.8 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 9.5Hz, C ₃ and C ₅ , Ar-H)
3b	Isonicotinoyl	—	—	C ₈ H ₈ N ₂ OCl	52	69	4.35 (2H, s, CH ₂ Cl), 7.5–8.5 (4H, m, proton of pyridine ring)
4a ₁	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	H	NHCOCH ₃	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₃ S	50	190	2.1 (3H, s, COCH ₃), 3.65 (2H, s, CH ₂), 3.55 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 6.8–7.7 (8H, m, Ar-H)
4a ₂	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	CH ₃	NHCOCH ₃	C ₁₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₃ S	85	218	2.1 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 2.2 (3H, s, Ar-CH ₃), 3.65 (2H, s, CH ₂ N), 4.35 (2H, s, OCH ₃), 7.1–7.5 (7H, m, pyridine ring protons), 8.5 (H, s ¹ br, SO ₂ NH)
4b ₁	Isonicotinoyl	H	NHCOCH ₃	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₃ S	80	117	2.5 (3H, s, COCH ₃), 3.65 (2H, s, CH ₂ N), 8.2–9.2 (4H, m, pyridine ring protons)
4c ₁	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	H	NHCOCH ₃	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ SOCl	86	138	2.1 (3H, s, COCH ₃), 2.2 (3H, s, Ar-CH ₃), 3.65 (2H, s, CH ₂ N), 4.37 (2H, s, OCH ₃), 7–7.6 (2H, m, Ar-H), 8.4 (1H, s br, NHSO ₂)
4c ₂	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	CH ₃	NHCOCH ₃	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ SOCl	90	125	2.3 (3H, s, Ar-CH ₃), 3.65 (2H, s, CH ₂ N), 4.55 (2H, s, OCH ₃), 7.1–7.5 (4H, m, Ar-H)
4c ₃	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	H	H	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ SOCl	95	172	3.7 (2H, s, CH ₂ N), 4.55 (2H, s, OCH ₃), 7.1–7.55 (9H, m, Ar-H)

absorption frequency at 1 670 cm⁻¹ in the product 2 and shifting of nmr signals. Compound 3 when reacted with substituted-sulphonamides yielded 4, the formation of which was explained on the basis of nmr spectra that the signal due to —CH₂Cl at δ 4.50 shifted to δ 3.65.

The hydrazides were prepared according to the procedure available in literature⁹. The following general method was used for the synthesis of the 1,3,4-oxadiazoles. The physical data of the compounds are given in the Table 1.

N-Chloroacetyl-*p*-chlorophenylacetyl hydrazide (2c): The mixture of *p*-chlorophenylacetyl hydrazide (20.05 g, 0.1 mol) and chloroacetyl chloride (11.3 g, 0.1 mol) was heated at 80° on a water-bath for 3 h and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The residue was washed with little alcohol and recrystallised from it to furnish 3 (18.0 g, 75%), m.p. 172° (Found: C, 46.30; H, 3.07; N, 10.75. C₁₀H₁₀N₂O₂Cl₂ requires: C, 46.33; H, 3.088; N, 10.81%) ; λ_{max} (ethanol) 280 nm ; ν_{max} (nujol) 3 250 (NH), 1 670 (C=O) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (phenyl) ; δ (TFA) 4.0 (2H, s, CH₂Cl), 4.55 (2H, s, OCH₃), 6.95 (2H, d, *J* 9Hz, C₂ and C₆, Ar-H) and 7.2 (2H, d, *J* 9Hz, C₃ and C₅, Ar-H).

5-(*p*-Chlorophenoxy)-2-chloromethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (3c): It was prepared by catalytic cyclisation of compound 2 (27.7 g, 0.1 mol) in phosphorus oxychloride (20 ml) for ~5 h. The unreacted POCl₃ was removed under reduced pressure and the residue triturated with ice-cold water. The extraction of the residue with ether gave a solid which was recrystallised from ethanol to furnish 3 (16 g, 60%), m.p. 81°, λ_{max} (ethanol) 280 nm ; ν_{max} (nujol) 1 630 (C=N) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (phenyl) ; δ (TFA) 4.55 (2H, s, OCH₂), 4.5 (2H, s, CH₂Cl) and 7.2–7.6 (4H, m, Ar-H).

5-(*p*-Chlorophenoxy)-2-(*p*-acetamidophenylsulphonamidyl)methyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (4c): To a mixture of 3c (0.129 g, 0.0005 mol) and *p*-acetamidobenzene sulphonamide (0.107 g, 0.0005 mol) in methanol (5 ml), anhydrous potassium carbonate (1.0 g) was added and the mixture was refluxed on a oil-bath at 250° for 5 h, then cooled and filtered. The residue was recrystallised from ethanol to give 4c (0.220 g, 95%), m.p. 140° (Found: C, 49.40; H, 3.80; N, 12.80. C₁₈H₁₇N₄O₅SOCl requires: C, 49.48; H, 3.85; N, 12.83%) ; λ_{max} (ethanol) 285 nm ; ν_{max} (nujol) 3 300 (NH), 1 670 (NHCO), 1 620 (C=N) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (phenyl) ; δ (TFA) 2.1 (3H,

s, COCH₃), 3.65 (2H, s, CH₂-N), 4.45 (2H, s, OCH₃) and 7.2-7.7 (8H, m, Ar-H).

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Studies on 4(3H)-Quinazolinone Derivatives as Antimalarials

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4(3H)-Quinazolinones are associated with broad spectrum biological activities¹⁻⁴. The high antimalarial activity of febrifugine⁵, an alkaloid with 3-substituted-4(3H)-quinazolinone structure, initiated the preparation and testing of several quinazolinones⁶⁻⁹ as potential antimalarials. Sengupta *et al.*¹⁰ showed that 2-mercapto-3-allyl-4(3H)-quinazolinone and its 6-methyl analogue were active antimalarials at 4 quinine equivalent of dosage¹⁰. Recently, 6-bromo-3-phenyl-2-(N,N-diethylcarbamoylmethyl)thio-4(3H)-quinazolinone and 6-bromo-3-m-chlorophenyl-2-(N,N-ethylphenylcarbamoylmethyl)thio-4(3H)-quinazolinone have been found to be active against *P. gallinaceum* in chicks¹¹. Considering these facts and that the biological activity of compounds is influenced by various substituents and their positions, a number of 2-(N,N-disubstituted-aminoethylthio)-3-alkyl/aryl-6-iodo-4(3H)-quinazolinones having the general structure 2 have been synthesised for testing their antimalarial activity.

The synthetic procedure to obtain these compounds (2) was alkylation of the sodium salt of the corresponding 2-thio-3-alkyl/aryl-6-iodo-4(3H)-quinazolinones (1) with the appropriate 2-(N-substituted or N,N-disubstituted amino)ethyl bromide hydrobromide salts¹. The intermediates (1) were synthesised by refluxing 5-iodoanthranilic acid with various alkyl/aryl-isothiocyanates. The synthesis of 4(3H)-quinazolinones (2) with 3-aryl substituents has been published elsewhere¹.

In addition, a model experiment on the benzoylation of 2-thio-3-methyl-4(3H)-quinazolinone was carried out. The product 2-benzoylthio-3-methyl-4(3H)-quinazolinone (3) when subjected to acid hydrolysis gave the corresponding sulphur free hydroxy compound 3-methyl-2,4(1H, 3H)-quinazolidione¹² (4). This shows that like alkylation^{12,13}, acylation also takes place at the sulphur atom at position-2 of the heterocyclic system. An unequivocal proof of the structure of 3 is provided by an unambiguous synthesis of its structural isomer (5) from N-benzoylanthranilic acid and methyl isothiocyanate. The two compounds 3 (m.p. 248°) and 5 (m.p. 95°) differ widely in melting point and show non-superimposable infrared spectra particularly in the fingerprint region.

In all thirteen representative compounds (no. 7 and twelve others published earlier¹) were screened for their antimalarial activity in mice infected with *P. berghei*; all of them were found to be inactive at 1 quinine equivalent of dosage. The animals were administered oral doses of 32 mg of the test compounds per kg body weight twice daily for 3 days; in untreated mice used as control parasitaemia was comparable to treated groups at the end of the treatment. The tests were carried out at the National Institute of Communicable Diseases, Delhi.